

KEY DIGITAL PRESERVATION TOOLS AND HOW TO USE THEM

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Abstract – This workshop is a hands-on workshop for first-time conference attendees and experienced practitioners. It will cover the steps in a Digital Curation workflow, and how and why the selected tools are important for and used at various points in the workflow. The tools chosen and workflow steps are based on the authors own knowledge, skills and work experience, rather than a comprehensive evaluation of all available digital preservation tools. It will also provide a forum for issue resolution that people may be facing in integrating and using these tools within a Digital Curation workflow.

To manage expectations and ensure a useful workshop, there will ideally be at least 3 facilitators (availability still pending), limited to approximately 3 hours and 15-20 participants (upon the advice and decision of the iPres Committee). At the time of this re-submission, there are potentially three facilitators, although in person availability is dependent upon pending government approval to attend the conference. While the author will also seek other potential attendees as facilitators via call-outs to the DPC and iPres2025 committee in the following months, nothing is definite yet (please let me know if finalising the program means that this workshop is not likely to occur).

The workshop will begin by going over the steps (Phases and Stages) of a Digital Curation workflow in which the author has experience (est. 30 minutes).

These include:

- Collect (Acquisition and transfer)
- Describe (Arrangement and Description)
- Preserve (Pre-ingest and Ingestion)
- Access (Store, manage and discover)

The workshop will provide a series of hands-on activities relating to the significance and use of the tools listed below:

- Exiftool (Collect, Describe and Preserve phases). Est. 30 minutes duration
- DROID and PRONOM (Describe and Preserve phases). Est. 20 minutes duration
- Hexadecimal editors eg. HxD (Preserve and Access phase). Est. 30 minute duration
- Bagger and the BagIt structure (Collect and Preserve phase). Est. 25 minutes duration

Time and interest permitting, I would also lead a discussion on the purpose and utility of disk imaging compared to file transfers (Describe, Preserve and Access phases). Est. 20 minutes.

Some discussion and activities may be structured to accommodate interest from the iPres2025 attendees via a pre-conference questionnaire / poll sent for distribution by the authors to Nicola Caldwell, Digital Archivist at the Alexander Turnbull Library (part of one of the iPres2025 Committees).

Participants will attempt exercises using a sample data set (either provided or their own). Discussion

will focus on what tools are used at other institutions and how they have solved or hope to resolve workflow issues. Discussion will also raise how funding, staffing and organisational size can introduce workflow limitations for some. The workshop will be approximately 3 hours (task breakdown provided above), with at least 20 minutes discussion at the end if possible, allowing 30 minutes for any technical issues. This would be the first instance of this workshop at a conference. The ideal space would be a meeting room large enough to hold participants with a presenting monitor at the front for screen sharing.

By the end of this workshop, participants should:

- Understand key steps in Digital Curation workflows as well as how and why different tools are useful across the workflow.
- Develop an understanding of how to do the following tasks:
 - o File format identification and characterisation.
 - o How to use Exiftool, DROID and PRONOM to analyse, describe and prepare acquisitions for preservation.
 - o Use of Hexadecimal editors to identify and correct files via internal signatures.
 - o Potential ways to package material into Submission Information Packages (SIPs) for digital preservation systems.
- Understanding common issues participants have faced or may face using these tools and how to solve them
- Understanding of purpose and utility of disk imaging compared to file transfer (discussion only - time permitting).

Submission Type – Workshop

Keywords – Skills, Training, Preservation Tools

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

This workshop will use a sample dataset to demonstrate some common digital preservation tools and how they fulfill different phases of a Digital Curation workflow: Collect, Describe, Preserve and Access. It is aimed at two audiences: first-time attendees relatively new to digital preservation, and more experienced practitioners who have used these tools and noted some difficulties in how best to use them. It is hoped that some of the experienced

practitioners may also provide facilitator support and assistance to this first-time workshop run by a first-time early career attendee. The aim is to increase digital preservation knowledge and skills amongst practitioners whilst providing a useful forum for discussion and issue resolution. Workshop activities will utilise a combination of the author's work experience across multiple institutions, interview tasks completed for digital preservation positions and adapt online and in-person training he has completed. This includes online training provided via the DPC and Australasia Preserves groups, as well as in-person training provided by current and previous managers, Joanna Fleming (Art Gallery of New South Wales) and Matthew Burgess (State Library of New South Wales). Please note that both people have indicated they will not be able to act as facilitators during this workshop.

The tools will be provided in the following ways:

- I) Participants will download and install the above tools on their laptops prior to the workshop. This can either be self-directed, via email or via a Google Drive or similar location to which the author has download the tools, accompanying installation instructions, workshop activities and sample dataset prior to the workshop. For simplicity, this email or shared OneDrive/ Google Drive location could be one nominated by the iPres Committee for attendees to access.
- II) Where Participants cannot download and install the applications to their work computers due to ICT policies etc, the author and facilitators will provide up to 2 laptops pre-installed with the tools for use during the workshop.
- III) Where participants have trouble installing the tools despite the provided instructions, the facilitators will provide a quick tutorial session prior to the Conference week (details TBD) to assist. This will save time during the workshop.

II. WORKSHOP ACTIVITIES

A. Exiftool

Workshop activities will include how to install and use exiftool via the command line to survey carriers to determine and assist with

identifying and funding potential preservation projects. For example, if you identify that a collection contains 500 yet-to-be preserved carriers, and 80% of these are 3.5-inch floppies, it could provide the basis to justify funding to purchase a 3.5 inch floppy and the staffing to prepare and preserve those carriers before the carriers become completely inaccessible. Activities will show how to analyse files and extract metadata for pre-ingest preparation activities. Will include how to use with disk images to determine software and hardware requirements for emulation purposes.

B. *DROID*

How to use DROID to investigate the file format and PRONOM PUID to characterise files. How to interpret and resolve common issues with DROID outputs using PRONOM and a hexadecimal editor. This could be multiple file formats identified, incorrect extension, or no identification at all.

C. *Hexadecimal editors*

What hexadecimal editors do and how to use them to identify file formats based on existing file format identification registries including PRONOM. Potential ways of editing files to fix access and corruption issues, as well as redact sensitive personal information.

D. *Bagger*

How to install and open Bagger. Discussion on bagging to the network or external storage. I will demonstrate how to create a Bagger profile for institutional metadata, ways to automate bagging all files within a directory, and common issues with validating bags (such as tagmanifest files or incorrect Payload Oxums).

III. DISCUSSION (TIME PERMITTING)

E. *Disk Imaging*

Discussion of how and when disk imaging fits into workflows and when file transfer is good enough. Discussion will highlight the need for disk imaging obsolete media, and where the directory structure is significant to the object itself, or its operation. This could be for

software where there are operations dependent on the location of dll files to execute functions to make that software operate correctly. It will also note imaging for public access requests where format migrations might be needed for access, such as with FileMaker Pro databases and the potential multiple format migrations required to provide access.

IV. CONCLUSION

There are a wide range of digital preservation tools available and used across cultural institutions. This workshop will introduce their functionality and importance to the early career professional, while also providing a good discussion forum for resolution of ongoing issues by more experienced practitioners.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

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